

Modular Equations for Ramanujan's Cubic Continued Fraction And its Evaluations

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Abstract: In this paper, we establish certain modular equations related to Ramanujan's cubic continued fraction

$$G(q) := \frac{q^{1/3}}{1 + \frac{q+q^2}{1 + \frac{q^2+q^4}{1 + \dots}}}, \quad |q| < 1.$$

and obtain many explicit values of $G(e^{-\pi\sqrt{n}})$, for certain values of n .

Key Words: Ramanujan cubic continued fraction, theta functions, modular equation.

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§1. Introduction

Let

$$G(q) := \frac{q^{1/3}}{1 + \frac{q+q^2}{1 + \frac{q^2+q^4}{1 + \dots}}}, \quad (1.1)$$

denote the Ramanujan's cubic continued fraction for $|q| < 1$. This continued fraction was recorded by Ramanujan in his second letter to Hardy [12]. Chan [11] and Baruah [5] have proved several elegant theorems for $G(q)$. Berndt, Chan and Zhang [8] have proved some general formulas for $G(e^{-\pi\sqrt{n}})$ and $H(e^{-\pi\sqrt{n}})$ where

$$H(q) := -G(-q)$$

and n is any positive rational, in terms of Ramanujan-Weber class invariant G_n and g_n :

$$G_n := 2^{-1/4} q^{-1/24} (-q; q^2)_\infty$$

and

$$g_n := 2^{-1/4} q^{-1/24} (q; q^2)_\infty, q = e^{-\pi\sqrt{n}}.$$

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For the wonderful introduction to Ramanujan's continued fraction see [3], [6], [11] and for some beautiful subsequent work on Ramanujan's cubic continued fraction [1], [2], [4], [5], [14] and [15].

In this paper, we establish certain general formulae for evaluating $G(q)$. In section 2 of this paper, we setup some preliminaries which are required to prove the general formulae. In section 3, we establish certain modular equations related to $G(q)$ and in the final section, we deduce the above stated general formulae and obtain many explicit values of $G(q)$. We conclude this introduction by recalling an identity for $G(q)$ stated by Ramanujan.

$$1 + \frac{1}{G^3(q)} = \frac{\psi^4(q)}{q\psi^4(q^3)} \quad (1.2)$$

where

$$\psi(q) := \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^{n(n+1)/2} = \frac{(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}}{(q; q^2)_{\infty}}. \quad (1.3)$$

The proof of (1.2) follows from Entry 1 (ii) and (iii) of Chapter 20 (6, p.345).

§2. Some Preliminary Results

As usual, for any complex number a ,

$$(a; q)_0 := 1$$

and

$$(a; q)_{\infty} := \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} (1 - aq^n), \quad |q| < 1.$$

A modular equation of degree n is an equation relating α and β that is induced by

$$n \frac{{}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; 1; 1 - \alpha\right)}{{}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; 1; \alpha\right)} = \frac{{}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; 1; 1 - \beta\right)}{{}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; 1; \beta\right)},$$

where

$${}_2F_1(a, b; c; x) := \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_n (b)_n}{(c)_n n!} x^n, \quad |x| < 1,$$

with

$$(a)_n := a(a+1)(a+2)\dots(a+n-1).$$

Then, we say that β is of n^{th} degree over α and call the ratio

$$m := \frac{z_1}{z_n},$$

the multiplier, where $z_1 = {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; 1; \alpha\right)$ and $z_n = {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; 1; \beta\right)$.

Theorem 2.1 *Let $G(q)$ be as defined as in (1.1), then*

$$G(q) + G(-q) + 2G^2(-q)G^2(q) = 0 \quad (2.1)$$

and

$$G^2(q) + 2G^2(q^2)G(q) - G(q^2) = 0. \quad (2.2)$$

For a proof of Theorem 2.1, see [11].

Theorem 2.2 *Let β and γ be of the third and ninth degrees, respectively, with respect to α . Let $m = z_1/z_3$ and $m' = z_3/z_9$. Then,*

$$(i) \quad \left(\frac{\beta^2}{\alpha\gamma}\right)^{1/4} + \left(\frac{(1-\beta)^2}{(1-\alpha)(1-\gamma)}\right)^{1/4} - \left(\frac{\beta^2(1-\beta)^2}{\alpha\gamma(1-\alpha)(1-\gamma)}\right)^{1/4} = \frac{-3m}{m'} \quad (2.3)$$

and

$$(ii) \quad \left(\frac{\alpha\gamma}{\beta^2}\right)^{1/4} + \left(\frac{(1-\alpha)(1-\gamma)}{(1-\beta)^2}\right)^{1/4} - \left(\frac{\alpha\gamma(1-\alpha)(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2(1-\beta)^2}\right)^{1/4} = \frac{m'}{m}. \quad (2.4)$$

For a proof, see [6], Entry 3 (xii) and (xiii), pp. 352-353.

Theorem 2.3 *Let α , β , γ and δ be of the first, third, fifth and fifteenth degrees respectively. Let m denote the multiplier connecting α and β and let m' be the multiplier relating γ and δ . Then,*

$$(i) \quad \left(\frac{\alpha\delta}{\beta\gamma}\right)^{1/8} + \left(\frac{(1-\alpha)(1-\delta)}{(1-\beta)(1-\gamma)}\right)^{1/8} - \left(\frac{\alpha\delta(1-\alpha)(1-\delta)}{\beta\gamma(1-\beta)(1-\gamma)}\right)^{1/8} = \sqrt{\frac{m'}{m}} \quad (2.5)$$

and

$$(ii) \quad \left(\frac{\beta\gamma}{\alpha\delta}\right)^{1/8} + \left(\frac{(1-\beta)(1-\gamma)}{(1-\alpha)(1-\delta)}\right)^{1/8} - \left(\frac{\beta\gamma(1-\beta)(1-\gamma)}{\alpha\delta(1-\alpha)(1-\delta)}\right)^{1/8} = -\sqrt{\frac{m}{m'}}. \quad (2.6)$$

For a proof, see [6], Entry 11 (viii) and (ix), p. 383.

Theorem 2.4 *If β , γ and δ are of degrees 3, 7 and 21 respectively, $m = z_1/z_3$ and $m' = z_7/z_{21}$, then*

$$(i) \quad \left(\frac{\beta\delta}{\alpha\gamma}\right)^{1/4} + \left(\frac{(1-\beta)(1-\delta)}{(1-\alpha)(1-\gamma)}\right)^{1/4} + \left(\frac{\beta\delta(1-\beta)(1-\delta)}{\alpha\gamma(1-\alpha)(1-\gamma)}\right)^{1/4} \\ - 2 \left(\frac{\beta\delta(1-\beta)(1-\delta)}{\alpha\gamma(1-\alpha)(1-\gamma)}\right)^{1/8} \left\{ 1 + \left(\frac{\beta\delta}{\alpha\gamma}\right)^{1/8} + \left(\frac{(1-\beta)(1-\delta)}{(1-\alpha)(1-\gamma)}\right)^{1/8} \right\} = mm' \quad (2.7)$$

and

$$(ii) \quad \left(\frac{\alpha\gamma}{\beta\delta}\right)^{1/4} + \left(\frac{(1-\alpha)(1-\gamma)}{(1-\beta)(1-\delta)}\right)^{1/4} + \left(\frac{\alpha\gamma(1-\alpha)(1-\gamma)}{\beta\delta(1-\beta)(1-\delta)}\right)^{1/4} \\ - 2 \left(\frac{\alpha\gamma(1-\alpha)(1-\gamma)}{\beta\delta(1-\beta)(1-\delta)}\right)^{1/8} \left\{ 1 + \left(\frac{\alpha\gamma}{\beta\delta}\right)^{1/8} + \left(\frac{(1-\alpha)(1-\gamma)}{(1-\beta)(1-\delta)}\right)^{1/8} \right\} = \frac{9}{mm'}. \quad (2.8)$$

For a proof, see [6], Entry 13 (v) and (vi), pp. 400-401.

§3. Modular Equations

Theorem 3.1 *Let*

$$R := \frac{\psi(-q^3)\psi(-q^2)}{q^{3/8}\psi(-q)\psi(-q^6)} \quad \text{and} \quad S := \frac{\psi(-q^6)\psi(-q^4)}{q^{3/4}\psi(-q^2)\psi(-q^{12})}$$

then,

$$\left(\sqrt{\frac{R}{S}} + \sqrt{\frac{S}{R}} \right) \left(\sqrt{RS} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{RS}} \right) - 8 = 0. \quad (3.1)$$

Proof From (1.2) and the definition of R and S , it can be seen that

$$B^3(A^3 + 1)R^4 = A^3(B^3 + 1) \quad (3.2)$$

and

$$C^3(B^3 + 1)S^4 = B^3(C^3 + 1), \quad (3.3)$$

where $A = G(-q)$, $B = G(-q^2)$ and $C = G(-q^4)$.

On changing q to q^2 in (2.1), we have

$$G(q^2) + G(-q^2) + 2G^2(-q^2)G^2(q^2) = 0 \quad (3.4)$$

and also change q to $-q$ in (2.2), we have

$$G^2(-q) + 2G^2(q^2)G(-q) - G(q^2) = 0. \quad (3.5)$$

Eliminating $G(q^2)$ between (3.4) and (3.5) using Maple,

$$2(AB)^4 - 4(AB)^3 + 3(AB)^2 + AB + A^3 + B^3 = 0. \quad (3.6)$$

Now on eliminating A between (3.2) and (3.6) using Maple, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &8(BR)^4 - 80(BR)^3 + 63(BR)^2 - 5BR + B^3 - 16B^3R + 72B^3R^2 + 7B^3R^4 \\ &- 22B^2R + 2B^2 + 2B^2R^3 - B^2R^4 - 9BR^2 + BR^3 + B + R = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (3.7)$$

Changing q to q^2 in (3.6),

$$2(BC)^4 - 4(BC)^3 + 3(BC)^2 + BC + B^3 + C^3 = 0. \quad (3.8)$$

Eliminating C between (3.3) and (3.8) using Maple,

$$\begin{aligned} &8B^4 + 7B^3 - 16S^3B^3 + 72S^2B^3 - 80SB^3 + S^4B^3 + 2B^2S^4 - B^2 + 2B^2S - 22S^3B^2 \\ &+ 63B^2S^2 - 9BS^2 + SB - 5BS^3 + BS^4 + S^3 = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (3.9)$$

Finally on eliminating B between (3.7) and (3.9) using Maple, we have

$$L(R, S)M(R, S) = 0,$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned}
 L(R, S) = & 15S^3R^6 - 1734R^4S^4 + SR + 49S^2R^2 - S^3 - 137S^4R^2 + 8S^4R + 705S^4R^3 \\
 & -137S^2R^4 - 8S^2R - 15S^2R^3 + 8SR^4 - 8SR^2 + 16SR^3 + 705S^3R^4 - 15S^3R^2 + 16S^3R - 327S^3R^3 \\
 & -120S^3R^5 + 705R^5S^4 + 15S^2R^5 - SR^5 - S^3R^7 - 137R^6S^4 + 8R^7S^4 - 327R^5S^5 + 49R^6S^6 \\
 & +8R^4S^7 - R^5S^8 - 15R^5S^6 - 8R^7S^6 - R^8S^5 - 15R^6S^5 + 16R^7S^5 - 8R^6S^7 + 16R^5S^7 + R^7S^7 \\
 & -120S^5R^3 + 15S^5R^2 + 705S^5R^4 - 137S^6R^4 + 15S^6R^3 - S^7R^3 - S^5R - R^3 = 0
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$M(R, S) = R^2S + RS^2 - 8RS + R + S = 0.$$

Using the series expansion of R and S in the above we find that

$$L(R, S) = 223522 + 8q^{-15/2} - 8q^{-57/8} - 2q^{-55/8} - 56q^{-27/4} + 48q^{-13/2} - 24q^{-49/8} + \dots$$

and

$$M(R, S) = q^{-15/8} + q^{-3/2} - 8q^{-9/8} + q^{-7/8} + q^{-3/4} + 2q^{-1/2} + \dots,$$

where

$$R = \frac{1}{q^{3/8}} + q^{5/8} + 2q^{29/8} + 2q^{21/8} + 2q^{13/8} + \dots$$

and

$$S = \frac{1}{q^{3/4}} + q^{5/4} + 2q^{29/4} + 2q^{21/4} + 2q^{13/4} + \dots$$

One can see that $q^{-1}L(R, S)$ does not tend to 0 as $q \rightarrow 0$ whereas $q^{-1}M(R, S)$ tends to 0 as $q \rightarrow 0$. Hence, $q^{-1}M(R, S) = 0$ in some neighborhood of $q = 0$. By analytic continuation $q^{-1}M(R, S) = 0$ in $|q| < 1$. Thus we have

$$M(R, S) = 0.$$

On dividing throughout by RS we have the result. □

Theorem 3.2 *If*

$$R := \frac{\psi^2(-q^3)}{q^{1/2}\psi(-q)\psi(-q^9)} \quad \text{and} \quad S := \frac{\psi^2(-q^6)}{q\psi(-q^2)\psi(-q^{18})},$$

then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left(\frac{R}{S}\right)^4 + \left(\frac{S}{R}\right)^4 + \left(\frac{R}{S}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{S}{R}\right)^2 - \left(RS - \frac{3}{RS}\right) \left\{ \left(\frac{R}{S}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{S}{R}\right)^3 \right\} \\
 & - 3 \left(RS - \frac{3}{RS}\right) \left(\frac{R}{S} + \frac{S}{R}\right) - \left\{ (RS)^2 + \frac{9}{(RS)^2} \right\} - 6 = 0. \quad (3.10)
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof Let

$$P := \frac{\psi^2(q^3)}{q^{1/2}\psi(q)\psi(q^9)} \quad \text{and} \quad Q := \frac{\psi^2(q^6)}{q\psi(q^2)\psi(q^{18})}.$$

On using Entry 10 (ii) and (iii) of Chapter 17 in [6, p.122] in P and Q , we deduce

$$\frac{P}{Q} = \left(\frac{\alpha\gamma}{\beta^2} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{P^2}{Q} = \left(\frac{z_3^2}{z_1 z_9} \right)^{1/2}.$$

Employing these in (2.3) and (2.4) it is easy to see that

$$\left\{ \frac{(1-\beta)^2}{(1-\alpha)(1-\gamma)} \right\}^{1/4} = \frac{Q^2(3+P^2)}{P^2(Q^2-P^2)} \quad \text{and} \quad \left\{ \frac{(1-\alpha)(1-\gamma)}{(1-\beta)^2} \right\}^{1/4} = \frac{P^2(P^2-1)}{Q^2-P^2}.$$

Multiplying these two, we arrive at

$$P^4 - 4P^2Q^2 + Q^4 + 3Q^2 - P^4Q^2 = 0. \quad (3.11)$$

Changing q to $-q$ in the above,

$$R^4 - 4R^2Q^2 + Q^4 + 3Q^2 - R^4Q^2 = 0. \quad (3.12)$$

On eliminating Q between (3.11) and (3.12), we have

$$\begin{aligned} P^4R^4 - 5P^4 - 12P^2 + 16P^2R^2 + 4P^2R^4 - 11R^4 - 8R^6 - R^8 + 12R^2 + 4P^4R^2 \\ = (-4P^2 - P^4 + 4R^2 + R^4)\sqrt{6R^4 - 24R^2 + 8R^6 + R^8 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

On squaring the above and then factorizing, we have

$$P^4 - 2P^2R^2 + R^4 - P^4R^2 - P^2R^4 + 3P^2 + 3R^2 = 0. \quad (3.13)$$

Changing q to q^2 in (3.13), we have

$$Q^4 - 2Q^2S^2 + S^4 - Q^4S^2 - Q^2S^4 + 3Q^2 + 3S^2 = 0. \quad (3.14)$$

Eliminating Q between (3.12) and (3.14) and then on dividing throughout by $(RS)^4$ and on simplifying, we obtain the required result.

Theorem 3.3 *If*

$$R := \frac{\psi(-q^3)\psi(-q^5)}{q^{1/4}\psi(-q)\psi(-q^{15})} \quad \text{and} \quad S := \frac{\psi(-q^6)\psi(-q^{10})}{q^{1/2}\psi(-q^2)\psi(-q^{30})},$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{R^2}{S^2} + \frac{S^2}{R^2} \right) + \left(\frac{R}{S} + \frac{S}{R} \right) - \left(\sqrt{RS} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{RS}} \right) \left\{ \sqrt{\frac{S}{R}} + \sqrt{\frac{R}{S}} + \left(\frac{R}{S} \right)^{3/2} + \left(\frac{S}{R} \right)^{3/2} \right\} \\ = RS + \frac{1}{RS}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.15)$$

Proof Let

$$P := \frac{\psi(q^3)\psi(q^5)}{q\psi(q)\psi(q^{15})} \quad \text{and} \quad Q := \frac{\psi(q^6)\psi(q^{10})}{q^2\psi(q^2)\psi(q^{30})},$$

On using Entry 11 (ii) and (iii) of Chapter 17 in [6, p.122] in P and Q we deduce

$$\frac{P}{Q} = \left(\frac{\alpha\delta}{\beta\gamma} \right)^{1/8} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{P^2}{Q} = \left(\frac{m'}{m} \right)^{1/2}.$$

Employing (2.5) and (2.6) in the above, it is easy to check that

$$\left(\frac{(1-\alpha)(1-\delta)}{(1-\beta)(1-\gamma)} \right)^{1/8} = \frac{P(P-1)}{Q-P} \quad \text{and} \quad \left(\frac{(1-\beta)(1-\gamma)}{(1-\alpha)(1-\delta)} \right)^{1/8} = \frac{Q(P+1)}{P(Q-P)}$$

Multiplying these two, we obtain

$$P^2 + Q^2 - 2PQ - P^2Q + Q = 0. \quad (3.16)$$

Changing q to $-q$ in the above

$$R^2 + Q^2 - 2RQ - R^2Q + Q = 0. \quad (3.17)$$

Eliminating Q between (3.16) and (3.17), we obtain

$$P^2 + R^2 + (P+R)(1-PR) = 0. \quad (3.18)$$

On Changing q to q^2 in the above

$$Q^2 + S^2 + (Q+S)(1-QS) = 0. \quad (3.19)$$

Finally, on eliminating Q between (3.17) and (3.19) and on dividing through out by $(RS)^2$, we have the result. $\square$

Theorem 3.4 *If*

$$R := q^2 \frac{\psi(-q^3)\psi(-q^{21})}{\psi(-q)\psi(-q^7)} \quad \text{and} \quad S := q^4 \frac{\psi(-q^6)\psi(-q^{42})}{\psi(-q^2)\psi(-q^{14})},$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} & y_8 - (4 + 6x_1)y_7 + (24 + 24x_1 + 9x_2)y_6 - (148 + 12x_1 + 36x_2)y_5 + (145 + 252x_1)y_4 \\ & - (648 + 678x_1 - 36x_2 + 54x_3)y_3 + (2180 + 360x_1 + 441x_2 - 324x_3)y_2 - (1016 + 2016x_1 - 396x_2 - 54x_3)y_1 \\ & + 81x_4 - 324x_3 + 1548x_2 + 1236x_1 + 5250 = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (3.20)$$

where

$$x_n = (3RS)^n + \frac{1}{(3RS)^n} \quad \text{and} \quad y_n = \left(\frac{R}{S} \right)^n + \left(\frac{S}{R} \right)^n.$$

Proof Let

$$P := q^2 \frac{\psi(q^3)\psi(q^{21})}{\psi(q)\psi(q^7)} \quad \text{and} \quad Q := q^4 \frac{\psi(q^6)\psi(q^{42})}{\psi(q^2)\psi(q^{14})},$$

Using Entry 11 (ii) and (iii) of Chapter 17 [6, p.122] in P and Q it is easy to deduce

$$\frac{P}{Q} = \left(\frac{\alpha\gamma}{\beta\delta} \right)^{1/8} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{P^2}{Q} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{mm'}}.$$

Employing (2.5) and (2.6) in the above, it is easy to check that

$$\left\{ \frac{(P-Q)^2 Px}{Q} - PQ - P^2 \right\}^2 - 4P^3Q - Q^2 + 2PQ - P^2 = 0$$

and

$$\left\{ \frac{(P-Q)^2}{Px} - P - Q \right\}^2 - 4PQ - 9P^2Q^2 + 18P^3Q - 9P^4 = 0.$$

where

$$x = \left(\frac{(1-\beta)(1-\delta)}{(1-\alpha)(1-\gamma)} \right)^{1/8}.$$

Eliminating x between these two we have

$$\begin{aligned} & Q^4 + 8Q^4P^2 - 4P^3Q^3 - 2P^4Q^2 - 44P^4Q^4 + 24Q^2P^6 - 12P^7Q + 81P^8Q^4 \\ & + 72P^6Q^4 - 18Q^2P^8 - 18Q^6P^4 - 36Q^5P^5 + P^8 + Q^8 - 2Q^6 - 12P^5Q^3 \\ & - 12P^3Q^5 + 24Q^6P^2 - 4Q^5P - 36P^7Q^3 - 12PQ^7 = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (3.21)$$

On changing q to $-q$ in the above

$$\begin{aligned} & Q^4 + 8Q^4R^2 - 4R^3Q^3 - 2R^4Q^2 - 44R^4Q^4 + 24Q^2R^6 - 12R^7Q + 81R^8Q^4 \\ & + 72R^6Q^4 - 18Q^2R^8 - 18Q^6R^4 - 36Q^5R^5 + R^8 + Q^8 - 2Q^6 - 12R^5Q^3 \\ & - 12R^3Q^5 + 24Q^6R^2 - 4Q^5R - 36R^7Q^3 - 12RQ^7 = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (3.22)$$

Now on eliminating Q between (3.21) and (3.22),

$$\begin{aligned} & R^4 - 2R^6 - 18P^8R^2 + 144P^7R^3 - 450P^6R^4 + 504P^5R^5 - 450P^4R^6 - 12PR^7 \\ & - 12RP^7 + 78R^2P^6 - 228R^3P^5 + 226R^4P^4 - 228R^5P^3 + 78R^6P^2 - 18R^8P^2 \\ & + P^4 - 2P^6 + P^8 + 81P^8R^4 + R^8 + 16RP^5 - 50R^2P^4 \\ & + 56R^3P^3 - 50R^4P^2 + 16R^5P + 144P^3R^7 - 4RP^3 + 6P^2R^2 - 4PR^3 \\ & + 486R^6P^6 - 324R^5P^7 - 324R^7P^5 + 81R^8P^4 = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (3.23)$$

On changing q to q^2 in the above

$$\begin{aligned} & Q^4 + Q^8 - 2Q^6 + S^4 - 2S^6 + S^8 - 18Q^8S^2 + 144Q^7S^3 - 450Q^6S^4 + 504Q^5S^5 \\ & - 450Q^4S^6 - 12QS^7 - 12SQ^7 + 78S^2Q^6 - 228S^3Q^5 + 226S^4Q^4 - 228S^5Q^3 \\ & + 78S^6Q^2 - 18S^8Q^2 + 81Q^8S^4 + 16SQ^5 - 50S^2Q^4 + 56S^3Q^3 \\ & - 50S^4Q^2 + 16S^5Q + 144Q^3S^7 - 4SQ^3 + 6Q^2S^2 - 4QS^3 + 486S^6Q^6 \\ & - 324S^5Q^7 - 324S^7Q^5 + 81S^8Q^4 = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (3.24)$$

Finally, on eliminating Q between (3.22) and (3.24), on dividing throughout by $(RS)^8$ and then simplifying we obtain the required result. $\square$

Theorem 3.5 *If*

$$P = \frac{\psi(q)}{q^{1/4}\psi(q^3)} \quad \text{and} \quad Q = \frac{\psi(q^7)}{q^{7/4}\psi(q^{21})}$$

then

$$(2(9 + (PQ)^4) \left(\left(\frac{P}{Q} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{Q}{P} \right)^2 \right) + 3(PQ)^4 + 27 = 15(PQ)^2 \left(\left(\frac{P}{Q} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{Q}{P} \right)^2 \right). \quad (3.25)$$

Proof Let

$$M_n := \frac{f(-q)}{q^{n/2}f(-q^{3n})}.$$

It is easy to see that

$$P = \frac{M_2^2}{M_1} \quad \text{and} \quad Q = \frac{M_{14}^2}{M_7},$$

which implies

$$M_1 = \frac{M_2^2}{P} \quad \text{and} \quad M_7 = \frac{M_{14}^2}{Q}. \quad (3.26)$$

From Entry 51 of Chapter 25 [7, p.204], we have

$$(M_1M_2)^2 + \frac{9}{(M_1M_2)^2} = \left(\frac{M_2}{M_1} \right)^6 + \left(\frac{M_1}{M_2} \right)^6. \quad (3.27)$$

Using (3.26) in (3.27), we deduce that

$$M_2^{12} = \frac{P^8(P^4 - 9)}{P^4 - 1}. \quad (3.28)$$

On changing q to q^7 in (3.28), we have

$$M_{14}^{12} = \frac{Q^8(Q^4 - 9)}{Q^4 - 1}.$$

Thus from the above and (3.28)

$$\left(\frac{M_2}{M_{14}} \right)^{12} = \frac{P^8(P^4 - 9)(Q^4 - 1)}{Q^8(P^4 - 1)(Q^4 - 9)}. \quad (3.29)$$

From Theorem 3.1(ii) of [9], we have

$$LM + \frac{1}{LM} = \left(\frac{L}{M} \right)^3 + \left(\frac{M}{L} \right)^3 + 4 \left(\frac{L}{M} + \frac{M}{L} \right), \quad (3.30)$$

where

$$L = \frac{M_1}{M_7} \quad \text{and} \quad M = \frac{M_2}{M_{14}}.$$

On using (3.26) in L , we obtain

$$L = \left(\frac{M_2}{M_{14}} \right)^2 \frac{Q}{P} \quad \text{and} \quad M = \frac{M_2}{M_{14}}.$$

Employing this in (3.30) and on dividing throughout by $(PQM_2/M_{14})^3$, we have

$$P^6 - 3 \left(\frac{M_2}{M_{14}} \right)^6 P^2 Q^4 - 3P^4 Q^2 - \left(\frac{M_2}{M_{14}} \right)^6 Q^6 = 0. \quad (3.31)$$

Finally, on eliminating M_2/M_{14} between (3.29) and (3.31) and on dividing throughout by $(PQ)^2$, we have the result. $\square$

§4. Evaluations of Ramanujan's Cubic Continued Fraction

Lemma 4.1 For $q = e^{-\pi\sqrt{n/3}}$, let

$$A_n := \frac{1}{\sqrt[4]{3}} \frac{\psi(-q)}{\psi(-q^3)}.$$

Then

$$(i) \quad A_n A_{1/n} = 1, \quad (4.1)$$

$$(ii) \quad A_1 = 1, \quad (4.2)$$

$$(iii) \quad H(q) = \frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{3A_n^4 + 1}}. \quad (4.3)$$

For a proof see [10].

Lemma 4.2

$$3A_n^2 A_{9n}^2 + \frac{3}{A_n^2 A_{9n}^2} = 3 + 6 \frac{A_{9n}^2}{A_n^2} + \frac{A_{9n}^4}{A_n^4}.$$

For a proof, see [10].

Lemma 4.3

$$\begin{aligned} 3(A_n A_{25n})^2 + \frac{3}{(A_n A_{25n})^2} &= \left(\frac{A_{25n}}{A_n} \right)^3 - \left(\frac{A_n}{A_{25n}} \right)^3 \\ + 5 \left(\frac{A_{25n}}{A_n} \right)^2 + 5 \left(\frac{A_n}{A_{25n}} \right)^2 + 5 \left(\frac{A_{25n}}{A_n} \right) - 5 \left(\frac{A_n}{A_{25n}} \right), \end{aligned}$$

For a proof, see [10].

Theorem 4.1 If A_n is as defined as in Lemma 4.1, then

$$\left(\sqrt{\frac{A_{4n}^2}{A_n A_{16n}}} + \sqrt{\frac{A_n A_{16n}}{A_{4n}^2}} \right) \left(\sqrt{\frac{A_{16n}}{A_n}} + \sqrt{\frac{A_n}{A_{16n}}} \right) = 8. \quad (4.4)$$

Proof For proof of (4.4), we use Theorem 3.1 with $R(q) = A_{4n}/A_n$ and $S = A_{16n}/A_{4n}$. $\square$

Theorem 4.2 We have

$$A_4 = 2 + \sqrt{3}$$

and

$$A_{1/4} = 2 - \sqrt{3}.$$

Proof Put $n = 1/4$ in (4.4) and using (4.1) we obtain the result. $\square$

Corollary 4.1 *We have*

$$H(e^{-\pi\sqrt{4/3}}) = \frac{1}{148}(292 + 168\sqrt{3})^{2/3}(73 - 42\sqrt{3})$$

and

$$H(e^{-\pi\sqrt{1/12}}) = \frac{1}{148}(292 - 168\sqrt{3})^{2/3}(73 + 42\sqrt{3}).$$

Proof On using Theorem 4.2 in (4.3), we have result. $\square$

Theorem 4.3 *If A_n is as defined as in Lemma 4.1, then*

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{A_{4n}A_{9n}}{A_nA_{36n}}\right)^4 + \left(\frac{A_nA_{36n}}{A_{4n}A_{9n}}\right)^4 + \left(\frac{A_{4n}A_{9n}}{A_nA_{36n}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{A_nA_{36n}}{A_{4n}A_{9n}}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{A_{9n}A_{36n}}{A_nA_{4n}} - 3\frac{A_nA_{4n}}{A_{9n}A_{36n}}\right) \\ & \times \left\{ \left(\frac{A_{4n}A_{9n}}{A_nA_{36n}}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{A_nA_{36n}}{A_{4n}A_{9n}}\right)^3 \right\} - 3 \left(\frac{A_{9n}A_{36n}}{A_nA_{4n}} - 3\frac{A_nA_{4n}}{A_{9n}A_{36n}}\right) \left(\frac{A_{4n}A_{9n}}{A_nA_{36n}} + \frac{A_nA_{36n}}{A_{4n}A_{9n}}\right) \\ & - \left\{ \left(\frac{A_{9n}A_{36n}}{A_nA_{4n}}\right)^2 + 9 \left(\frac{A_nA_{4n}}{A_{9n}A_{36n}}\right)^2 \right\} - 6 = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4.5)$$

Proof The proof is similar to Theorem 4.1 by applying Theorem 3.2. $\square$

Theorem 4.4 *We have*

$$A_6 = \sqrt[4]{6\sqrt{2} - 3\sqrt{3} + 3\sqrt{6}} - 6 = A_{1/6}^{-1}$$

and

$$A_{2/3} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \sqrt[4]{6\sqrt{2} + 3\sqrt{3} + 3\sqrt{6} + 6} = A_{3/2}^{-1}.$$

Proof Setting $n = 1/6$ in (4.5) and upon using (4.1), we find that

$$\left(\frac{A_6}{A_{2/3}}\right)^4 + 9 \left(\frac{A_{2/3}}{A_6}\right)^4 + 8 \left\{ \left(\frac{A_6}{A_{2/3}}\right)^2 - 3 \left(\frac{A_{2/3}}{A_6}\right)^2 \right\} + 2 = 0.$$

Since A_n is real and increasing in n , we have $A_6/A_{2/3} > 1$. Hence

$$\frac{A_6}{A_{2/3}} = \sqrt{3\sqrt{2} - 3}. \quad (4.6)$$

Again on setting $n = 2/3$ in Lemma 4.2, we have

$$3(A_{2/3}A_6)^2 + \frac{3}{(A_{2/3}A_6)^2} = 3 + 6\frac{A_6^2}{A_{2/3}^2} + \frac{A_6^4}{A_{2/3}^4}.$$

On using (4.6) in this, we obtain

$$A_{2/3}A_6 = \sqrt{2 + \sqrt{3}}. \quad (4.7)$$

Finally, on employing (4.6), (4.7) and (4.1) we have the result. $\square$

Corollary 4.2 *We have*

$$H(e^{-\pi\sqrt{2}}) = \frac{1}{(18\sqrt{2} - 9\sqrt{3} + 9\sqrt{6} - 17)^{1/3}}$$

and

$$H(e^{-\pi\sqrt{2/9}}) = \frac{1}{(18\sqrt{2} + 9\sqrt{3} + 9\sqrt{6} + 19)^{1/3}}.$$

Proof On using Theorem 4.4 in (4.3), we have the result. $\square$

Theorem 4.5 *If A_n is as defined as in Lemma 4.1, then*

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{A_{4n}A_{25n}}{A_nA_{100n}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{A_nA_{100n}}{A_{4n}A_{25n}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{A_{4n}A_{25n}}{A_nA_{100n}} + \frac{A_nA_{100n}}{A_{4n}A_{25n}} \right) - \left(\sqrt{\frac{A_{25n}A_{100n}}{A_nA_{4n}}} + \sqrt{\frac{A_nA_{4n}}{A_{25n}A_{100n}}} \right) \\ & \left(\sqrt{\frac{A_{4n}A_{25n}}{A_nA_{100n}}} + \sqrt{\frac{A_nA_{100n}}{A_{4n}A_{25n}}} + \left(\frac{A_{4n}A_{25n}}{A_nA_{100n}} \right)^{3/2} + \left(\frac{A_nA_{100n}}{A_{4n}A_{25n}} \right)^{3/2} \right) = \frac{A_{25n}A_{100n}}{A_nA_{4n}} + \frac{A_nA_{4n}}{A_{25n}A_{100n}}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.8)$$

Proof The proof is similar to Theorem 4.1 by using Theorem 3.3. $\square$

Theorem 4.6 *We have*

$$A_{10} = \sqrt{\frac{2 + \sqrt{10} + \sqrt{4\sqrt{10} + 10}}{2}} \sqrt[4]{\frac{a - \sqrt{a^2 - 36}}{6}} = A_{1/10}^{-1}$$

and

$$A_{2/5} = \sqrt{\frac{2 + \sqrt{10} - \sqrt{4\sqrt{10} + 10}}{2}} \sqrt[4]{\frac{a - \sqrt{a^2 - 36}}{6}} = A_{5/2}^{-1},$$

where $a = (18 + 4\sqrt{10})(\sqrt{4\sqrt{10} + 10}) + 60 + 20\sqrt{10}$.

Proof Setting $n = 1/10$ in (4.8) and upon using (4.1), we find that

$$x^2 + \frac{1}{x^2} - 4 \left(x + \frac{1}{x} \right) - 4 = 0,$$

where $x = A_{10}/A_{2/5}$. Since A_n is real and increasing in n , we have $A_{10}/A_{2/5} > 1$. Hence we choose

$$x + \frac{1}{x} = 2 + \sqrt{10}.$$

On solving

$$\frac{A_{10}}{A_{2/5}} = \frac{1}{2} \left(2 + \sqrt{10} + \sqrt{4\sqrt{10} + 10} \right). \quad (4.9)$$

Put $n = 2/5$ in Lemma 4.3, we have

$$\begin{aligned} 3(A_{2/5}A_{10})^2 + \frac{3}{(A_{2/5}A_{10})^2} &= \left(\frac{A_{10}}{A_{2/5}}\right)^3 - \left(\frac{A_{2/5}}{A_{10}}\right)^3 \\ &+ 5 \left\{ \left(\frac{A_{10}}{A_{2/5}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{A_{2/5}}{A_{10}}\right)^2 \right\} + 5 \left(\frac{A_{10}}{A_{2/5}} - \frac{A_{2/5}}{A_{10}} \right). \end{aligned}$$

On employing (4.9) in this, we obtain

$$A_{2/5}A_{10} = \sqrt{\frac{a - \sqrt{a^2 - 36}}{6}}, \quad (4.10)$$

where $a = (18 + 4\sqrt{10})(\sqrt{4\sqrt{10} + 10}) + 60 + 20\sqrt{10}$. On using (4.9) and (4.10) we have the result. $\square$

Theorem 4.7 *If A_n is as defined as in Lemma 4.1, then*

$$\begin{aligned} (2 + 2(A_nA_{49n})^4) \left[\left(\frac{A_n}{A_{49n}}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{A_{49n}}{A_n}\right)^2 \right] + 3(A_nA_{49n})^4 + 3 \\ = 5(A_nA_{49n})^2 \left[\left(\frac{A_n}{A_{49n}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{A_{49n}}{A_n}\right)^2 \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (4.11)$$

Proof The proof is similar to Theorem 4.1 by applying Theorem 3.5. $\square$

Theorem 4.8 *If A_n is as defined as in Lemma 4.1, then*

$$\begin{aligned} y_8 - (4 + 6x_1)y_7 + (24 + 24x_1 + 9x_2)y_6 - (148 + 12x_1 + 36x_2)y_5 + (145 + 252x_1)y_4 \\ - (648 + 678x_1 - 36x_2 + 54x_3)y_3 + (2180 + 360x_1 + 441x_2 - 324x_3)y_2 - (1016 + 2016x_1 - 396x_2 - 54x_3)y_1 \\ + 81x_4 - 324x_3 + 1548x_2 + 1236x_1 + 5250 = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (4.12)$$

where

$$x_m = (3A_nA_{4n}A_{49n}A_{196n})^m + \frac{1}{(3A_nA_{4n}A_{49n}A_{196n})^m}, \quad m = 1, 2, 3$$

and

$$y_m = \left(\frac{A_{49n}A_{196n}}{A_nA_{4n}}\right)^m + \left(\frac{A_nA_{4n}}{A_{49n}A_{196n}}\right)^m, \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, 8$$

Proof The proof is similar to Theorem 4.1 by applying Theorem 3.4. $\square$

Theorem 4.9 *We have*

$$A_{14} = \frac{1}{\sqrt[4]{34}} \{ (a + \sqrt{a^2 - 14})(9 + 10\sqrt{2}) \}^{1/4} = A_{1/14}^{-1}$$

and

$$A_{2/7} = \left(\frac{2}{17} \frac{9 + 10\sqrt{2}}{a + \sqrt{a^2 - 4}} \right)^{1/4} = A_{7/2}^{-1},$$

where

$$a = \frac{1}{3}(197 + 18\sqrt{113})^{1/3} + \frac{13}{3(197 + 18\sqrt{113})^{1/3}} + \frac{2}{3}.$$

Proof On setting $n = 1/14$ in (4.12) and upon using (4.1), we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \left(t^8 + \frac{1}{t^8}\right) &- 16 \left(t^7 + \frac{1}{t^7}\right) + 90 \left(t^6 + \frac{1}{t^6}\right) - 244 \left(t^5 + \frac{1}{t^5}\right) + 649 \left(t^4 + \frac{1}{t^4}\right) \\ &- 2040 \left(t^3 + \frac{1}{t^3}\right) + 3134 \left(t^2 + \frac{1}{t^2}\right) - 4148 \left(t + \frac{1}{t}\right) + 10332 = 0, \end{aligned}$$

where $t = (A_{2/7}A_{14})^2$. On setting $t + \frac{1}{t} = x$, we obtain

$$x^8 - 16x^7 + 82x^6 - 132x^5 + 129x^4 - 1044x^3 + 1332x^2 + 864x + 5184 = 0.$$

On solving this, we obtain

$$x = 6, \quad \frac{1}{3}(197 + 18\sqrt{113})^{1/3} + \frac{13}{3(197 + 18\sqrt{113})^{1/3}} + \frac{2}{3}$$

are the double roots and the remaining roots are imaginary. Since A_n is increasing in n , and solving for $(A_{14}/A_{2/7})^2$, it is easy to see that

$$\left(\frac{A_{14}}{A_{2/7}}\right)^2 = \frac{a + \sqrt{a^2 - 4}}{2},$$

where a is as defined earlier. On setting $n = 2/7$ in (4.11) and on using the above, we have the result. $\square$

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